

SELECTION OF THE OPTIMAL TYPE OF EXTRACTANT FOR OBTAINING EXTRACT FROM COMMON CORN (ZEA MAYS L.) RAW MATERIAL

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Relevance: Corn silk (*Zea mays* L.) is a source of biologically active substances (BAS), among which flavonoids are of particular importance. They have diuretic, anti-inflammatory, and choleric effects, which determines their pharmacological value. The effectiveness of obtaining standardized herbal preparations largely depends on the correct selection of an extractant that ensures the maximum yield of active substances. In this regard, it is relevant to study the extraction conditions that affect the extraction of flavonoids.

Objective: To select the type of extractant for obtaining an extract from the stigmas of *Zea mays* with the highest yield of flavonoids.

Materials and methods: Dried corn silk that met the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan was used as raw material. Extraction was carried out by maceration at a raw material-extractant ratio of 1:10. Maceration is a method of infusing plant raw materials in an extractant at room temperature with periodic stirring, which ensures gradual and uniform extraction of active substances. Water and alcohol solutions of various concentrations (40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80%, and 90%) were used as extractants. The quantitative determination of the total flavonoids was carried out by spectrophotometric method in terms of luteolin-7-glycoside.

Results: The analysis revealed that the concentration of the extractant has a significant effect on the yield of flavonoids. The highest peak value was recorded when using 60% ethanol.

Table 1

Results of spectrophotometric analysis of *Zea mays* L. extracts using various extractants

Extractant	Peak value, mg/ml
Water	0,095
40% ethanol	0,109
50% ethanol	0,036
60% ethanol	0,285
70% ethanol	0,176
80% ethanol	0,269
90% ethanol	0,119

In a 60% alcohol extract of corn silk, the quantitative content of flavonoids was determined by spectrophotometry in terms of luteolin-7-glycoside, amounting to 0.465%, which exceeds the norm of 0.35%.

Conclusions: The optimal extractant for obtaining a dry extract of corn silk by maceration is 60% ethanol, which ensures maximum flavonoid extraction. This approach allows obtaining a standardized extract with high biological activity, which opens up prospects for its further use in the development of dosage forms.